

Absolute Configurations of Goniiodiol, Goniiodiol Monoacetate and Other Related Dihydropyrones from Synthetic, Circular Dichroism and X-Ray Crystallographic Evidence^{Ψ#}

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The absolute configuration of (+)-goniiodiol [6-(7,8-dihydro-7,8-dihydroxystyryl)-5,6-dihydro-2-pyrone] (3) has been unambiguously and independently determined and revised as 7(R),8(R) from the circular dichroism (CD) studies of the diol and its dibenzoate. The 6(R) configuration that follows from its already reported 6,7-*threo* configuration is also confirmed by the CD spectrum of 3. Thus, the other congener chemically correlated natural dihydropyrans (+)-goniiodiol monoacetate (2), (+)-goniiodiol diacetate (1) and (+)-goniotriol (4), isolated from *Goniiothalamus sesquipedalis* (Annonaceae) must possess the same 6(R),7(R),8(R) absolute configuration. The 5(R) configuration of (+)-goniotriol (4) is predicted from the 5,6-*threo* configuration, based on the $J_{5,6}$ -value as well as from biogenetic ground. Synthetic evidences known in the literature for the absolute configuration of goniiodiol and some structurally related natural products have also been incorporated. The X-ray crystallographic structure determination of (+)-goniiodiol monoacetate (2) unambiguously confirms its 6,7-*threo* and 7,8-*erythro* relationship with 6(R),7(R),8(R) configuration. The molecular conformations in solution and crystalline state have also been studied.

Earlier, from this laboratory the isolation of four new 6-substituted-5,6-dihydro-2-pyrones was reported¹ from the leaves and twigs of the chemically virgin glabrous shrub *Goniiothalamus sesquipedalis* Wall.² (Fam. Annonaceae) collected from the hilly regions of Manipur where it grows abundantly. It is a well-known folk medicine : dried, powdered leaves are taken by local women during labour pain and its leaves are used as mosquito repellent by burning the same.

The detailed high resolution ¹H nmr and other spectral analyses along with their chemical interconversions revealed their structures as 6-(7,8-dihydro-7,8-diacetoxy-styryl)-5,6-dihydro-2-pyrone (1'), 6-(7,8-dihydro-7-acetoxy-8-hydroxystyryl)-5,6-dihydro-2-pyrone (2'), 6-(7,8-dihydro-7,8-dihydroxystyryl)-5,6-dihydro-2-pyrone (3') and 6-(7,8-dihydro-7,8-dihydroxystyryl)-5,6-dihydro-5-hydroxy-2-pyrone (4') which were designated goniiodiol diacetate (1'), goniiodiol monoacetate (2'), goniiodiol (3') and goniotriol (4') respectively¹. This shrub proved to be a rich source of 5,6-dihydro-2-pyrones. No such oxygenated 7,8-dihydro-styryl-5,6-dihydro-2-pyrone was reported earlier. A number of structurally similar natural products were found to possess significant biological activity³.

- 1' R¹ = R² = Ac, R = H
 2' R = R¹ = H, R² = Ac
 3' R = R¹ = R² = H
 4' R = OH, R¹ = R² = H

Relative configuration of the dihydropyrones :

The determination of the relative configuration of C-7 and C-8 in all the four pyrones (1'-4') was possible from a careful analysis of the vicinal coupling constant (J_{AB}) of H-7 and H-8 in each pyrone which was found to lie between 8.5 and 7.5 Hz, indicating^{4,5} that the dihedral angle $H_A-C-C-H_B$ in the preferred conformer should approach 180° and hence H_A and H_B should be *anti* and not *gauche*. J_{AB} is reduced by few Hz by other electronegative substituents^{6,7} like OR, NR₂, halogen etc. and the observed J_{AB} is the weighted average of the J_{AB} 's of all the conformers. Thus of the three possible conformers (a), (b) and (c) of goniiodiol (3') (Scheme 1), assumed to have 7,8-*erythro* configuration; only (a) has H_A and H_B in *anti* conformation which also was expected to be the most stable rotamer

Scheme 1

^ΨThis paper is dedicated to Professor T. R. Govindachari on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary with profound regards and best wishes.

[#]A part of the original work presented in this paper constituted the first chapter of Part 2 of the Ph D. Thesis of one of the authors (A.P.), submitted to the University of Calcutta in 1994.

Scheme 2

since the most bulky groups, Ph, and the dihydro lactone moiety are antiperiplanar. In the other two possible rotamers (b) and (c), the gain in stability due to possible intramolecular hydrogen bonding in a 5-membered ring was outweighed by the severe *gauche* interaction between the aforesaid bulky groups. Thus the preferred conformer (a) of the 7,8-*erythro* diastereomer was in agreement with the observed J_{AB} .

The alternate possibility having H_A and H_B in the *anti* position is the conformer (e) of the 7,8-*threo* diastereomer; but in this conformer also the severe *gauche* interaction between the most bulky groups outweighs the H-bonding stabilization. It was, therefore, predictable that for the *threo* diastereomer the conformer (d) having the bulky groups in *anti* position as well as the H-bonding stabilization would be the most abundant one, and the expected^{6,7} average J_{AB} for the *threo* diastereomer should be less than 4 Hz. Obviously, based on J_{AB} values, for all the dihydropyrones, 7,8-*erythro* configuration was predicted and the *threo* configuration was definitely ruled out.

Tentative absolute configuration :

(+)-Goniodiol (3') and its congener dihydropyrones were proposed² to have 6(*S*), 7(*S*), 8(*S*) configuration on the basis of the following two facts.

(a) (+)-Goniothalamine (5'), reported⁸ from several *Goniothalamus* species, is the most logical biogenetic precursor of all the dihydropyrones 1'-4'. It may be regarded as the cyclized form of precursors arising out of a cinnamic acid starter unit by increment of two C_2 units⁹. The C-6 position of (+)-goniothalamine (5) was shown to have (*S*)-configuration as follows : (+)-goniothalamine (5') was shown⁸ from its spectral and physical data to be identical with (+)-6(*S*)- δ -lactone of 5*S*-hydroxy-7-phenylhepta-2,6-dienoic acid (6'), previously isolated¹⁰ from the dried tree-bark of *Cryptocarya caloneura* (Scheff) Kostermans (Lauraceae). The 6(*S*) configuration of 5' was deduced¹⁰ by its chemical degradation and conversion to the xanthate of (-)-(*S*)-malic acid (arising from C-3, C-4, C-5 and C-6).

(b) It was envisaged¹ that in plant cells (+)-goniothalamine (5') underwent preferential enzymatic α -epoxidation (α -face or *Si-Si* face¹¹ being sterically less hindered) to form goniothalamine 7(*S*),8(*R*)-epoxide (7') which upon enzymatic acid catalyzed *trans*-opening by an S_N2 -

Scheme 3

type attack at the benzylic C-8 position would give rise to goniodiol (3') having 6(*S*),7(*S*),8(*S*) configuration (Scheme 2).

Revised absolute configuration of the dihydro-2-pyrones from chiral synthesis, biogenesis and interconversions :

Contrary to the previous contention^{8,10}, (+)-goniothalamine has been unambiguously established by its total synthesis^{12,13} to have 6(*R*) configuration (5) instead of 6(*S*) configuration (5') which necessitates the changing of the absolute configuration of (+)-goniodiol to the mirror image 3 having 6(*R*), 7(*R*), 8(*R*) configuration (Scheme 3). Now, as discussed earlier, it may be envisaged that in the plant cells (+)-goniothalamine (5) having 6(*R*) configuration undergoes enzymatic epoxidation from the less hindered *Re-Re* face¹⁰ (β -face in structure 5) to form goniothalamine 7(*R*), 8(*S*)-epoxide (7). This is followed by specific enzyme catalyzed *trans*-opening of the latter by the regioselective S_N2 attack by water at the benzylic C-8 position from the rear side of the C-O bond to form goniodiol (3) having 6(*R*), 7(*R*), 8(*R*) configuration. Subsequent enzymatic acetylation produces (+)-goniodiol monoacetate (2) and (+)-goniodiol diacetate (1) with 6(*R*), 7(*R*), 8(*R*) configuration (Scheme 3).

It may be mentioned here that (+)-goniothalamine 7,8-oxide was reported¹⁴ to occur in *Goniothalamus macrophyllus* and was proposed to have 6(*S*), 7(*R*), 8(*R*) configuration 7' based on the previous 6(*S*) configuration⁷ of (+)-goniothalamine and the value of the coupling constant¹⁵ ($J_{6,7}$ 5.4 Hz) showing *threo* configuration of C-6 and C-7; C-7 position was, however, incorrectly designated¹⁴ as (*R*) and should be (*S*).

deacetylation of the diacetate 1 to the monoacetate 2, (b) complete deacetylation of 1 to the diol 3, (c) acetylation of 3 to 2 and 1, (d) acetylation of 2 to 1, and (e) deacetylation of 2 to 3 (present work). Moreover, 1 upon allylic acetoxylation using SeO₂/AcOH-Ac₂O (1 : 1) gave goniotriol triacetate (4a).

The relative stereochemistry of C-5 in 4 was ascertained earlier¹. This can be settled from the ¹H nmr spectral analysis. The H-5 proton after deuteration appeared as a doublet¹ $J_{5,4}$ 6 and $J_{5,6}$ 4 Hz. The latter *J*-value at once indicates that H-5 and H-6 must be *gauche* and hence *cis* oriented leading to C₅, C₆ *threo* configuration. The 6*R*-configuration being already established for 1 to 4, the configuration of C-5 must be (*S*) as shown in 4.

A novel styrylpyrone, 9-deoxygoniopypyrone (9) and goniodiol (3) were isolated from the stem bark of *Goniothalamus giganteus* and shown to have cytotoxic activity¹⁶. The relative configurations of 3¹ and 9 were confirmed by X-ray crystallographic analysis¹⁶. The first enantioselective syntheses of 3 and 9 starting from 2,3-*O*-isopropylidene-D-glyceraldehyde were developed thus confirming their absolute configurations¹⁷. It is interesting to note that 9 possesses 1(*R*), 8(*R*) configuration corresponding to 6(*R*), 7(*R*) configuration of 3, but has 7(*S*) configuration, epimeric to the corresponding 8(*R*) configuration of 3. In this novel synthesis¹⁷, the new chiral centre 5(*R*) in 9 was generated after epimerization of C-8 of goniodiol 7-*O*-methoxymethyl ether followed by intramolecular stereospecific Michael addition of its 8-OH to its 4-position from diastereofacial *Re-Re* attack (β -face) (less hindered convex face) simply by treatment with 75% AcOH (65°, 4 h).

The enantiodivergent total syntheses of the antitumor (+)-altholactone (10), first isolated from an unknown *Polyalthaea* species¹⁸, and of its unnatural enantiomer (-)-altholactone have been developed starting from D-glucose¹⁹. The lactone 10, designated goniothalenol, was later isolated²⁰ from the stem bark of *Goniothalamus giganteus*; its structure was confirmed by X-ray analysis and it was shown to be cytotoxic *in vitro* (B5, 9 KB) and active *in vivo* against P388 leukemia²⁰. From the established absolute configuration of 4 and 10, it is apparent that 4 might get cyclized in presence of specific enzymes in plant cells to form 10 through the generation of the benzylic C-8 radical which couples with 5-O radical keeping the stereochemis-

In view of the 6(*R*) configuration in (+)-goniothalamine (5), this natural epoxide should be the enantiomer of the one shown¹⁴ and will have 6(*R*), 7(*R*), 8(*S*) configuration (7).

The following interconversions¹ (keeping the chiral centres unaffected) that were carried out earlier, unambiguously establish not only the structural relationship but also the same stereochemistry at the chiral centres C-6(*R*), C-7(*R*), C-8(*R*) of the dihydropyrones 1-4a : (a) partial

try of C-5 and C-8 unaffected. However, 6(*R*) configuration in 4 becomes 6(*S*) in 10 because of change in the priority sequence in the latter. It is, therefore, predicted that goniotriol (4), if subjected to radical catalyzed cyclization, might give rise to 10, but acid catalyzed cyclization would lead to a diastereomer of 10 with 8(*S*) configuration. Because of paucity of 4 its conversion to 10 or its 8-epimer could not be effected as yet.

A fresh supply of the leaves and twigs of *G. sesquipedalis* when subjected to the same isolation procedure¹ afforded after initial chromatography and purification through flash chromatography, 1, 2 and 3 but unfortunately 4 could not be isolated although its presence in traces could be detected in tlc. The absolute configuration of 3 and its dibenzoate 8 (prepared from 3) was confirmed from their circular dichroism study and conformational analyses as discussed in the sequel.

Absolute configuration of goniodiol and its dibenzoate from circular dichroism studies :

The same absolute configuration 6(*R*), 7(*R*), 8(*R*) has been independently determined by the following circular dichroism (CD) studies on (a) (+)-goniidiol (3) and (b) its molybdenum acetate complex, and (c) also on (+)-goniidiol dibenzoate (8)*.

Fig 1 CD Spectrum of (+)-goniidiol (3)

The lactone moiety of the (+)-goniidiol (3) in acetonitrile solution (c 0.304 mg g⁻¹) displayed in its CD spectrum a positive Cotton effect (Fig. 1) at 260 nm ($\Delta\epsilon$ 2.914) (the λ_{\max} for the α - β -unsaturated γ -lactone chromophore) which by application of Sznatzke's lactone chirality rule²¹ indicates clearly that the stereochemistry at the centre of

chirality C-6 in the lactone ring of the diol 3 is (*R*) and not (*S*). Thus the chirality in the ring is established as (*R*).

However, (+)-goniothalamin has recently been confirmed to have 6(*R*) configuration [and not 6(*S*) as previously ascribed¹⁰] by its chiral synthesis by two groups^{12,13}. Thus, (+)-goniothalamin with 6(*R*) configuration must be the biogenetic precursor of (+)-goniidiol (3) and other derived natural dihydropyrones like goniidiol diacetate (1), goniidiol monoacetate (2) and goniotriol (4).

The CD spectrum of the molybdenum acetate complex of goniidiol was also studied, but it was found to be practically just noise. This means that the diol of this type cannot be *threo*, in which case we would have expected²² a nice positive or negative CD around 300 nm (the absorption maximum for the complex). Thus, it was established, of course by default, that the diol must have *erythro* configuration [either 7(*R*), 8(*R*) or 7(*S*), 8(*S*)] as suggested earlier¹ from $J_{7,8}$ values. The small phenyl CD-band around 270 nm was too weak to be observed compared to the too strong lactone CD. As a result, even some fine structure-bands around 270 nm could not be seen. Thus, the absolute configurations of C-7 and C-8 could not be determined.

CD Study on α -glycol dibenzoates by exciton chirality method : An empirical method for the determination of the absolute configuration of 1,2-glycols was developed by Nakanishi and Harada²³ through the CD spectra of their dibenzoates (dibenzoate chirality rule, subsequently termed as the exciton chirality method²⁴).

The 230 nm band in an unsubstituted dibenzoate of 1,2-glycol is due to the intramolecular π - π^* charge transfer transition in which the electric transition moment (μ_e) is approximately parallel to the C-O bond of the ester. As the benzoate chromophore is inherently symmetric, the observed cotton effect (CE) necessarily arises from the asymmetric perturbation in a chiral environment. The benzoate chromophore exhibits three π - π^* absorption bands in the ultra-violet region, i.e. at 280 nm (ϵ 1000) due to the ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B$ (1L_b) transition of the benzene ring, at 230 nm (ϵ 14000) due to an intramolecular charge-transfer transition, and at 195 nm (ϵ 14000) due to the ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_1$ (1L_a) transition²⁵. The benzoates of the chiral vicinal diols exhibited CE only at around 225 nm, but no Cotton effect was observed at the other absorption bands. The presence of saturated ketone groups does not interfere with the interpretation²⁶, since Cotton effect due to ketone and benzoate groups differ greatly in position and intensity. Correct prediction was made even when the strongly optically active enone group was present²⁷.

In the case of vicinal dibenzoate, the two chromophores form a chiral screw pattern, either right-handed or left-handed. The result of the interaction of the two chromophores is the splitting of the Cotton effect into two. This

* The CD spectra of these compounds were received through the courtesy of an authority in the CD field, Late Professor G. Sznatzke of Ruhr University, Bochum.

Fig 2

splitting is called Davydov splitting²⁸. The first Cotton effect appears around 233 nm and the second one of equal intensity and of opposite sign around 219 nm. The sign of the first CE corresponds to the helicity rule, the right-handed screw pattern of *P* helicity showing a positive CE and the left-handed one of *M* helicity showing a negative CE (Fig. 2). This CE is one of the strongest CE's encountered in common molecules²⁹, and its position is fixed at about 233 nm.

Chirality of goniodiol dibenzoate (8) :

Other chromophores do not usually interfere with the Cotton effect because of the difference in its position and intensity. However, all the stable conformers of the dibenzoate should be considered for the application of the aforesaid chirality rule. (+)-Goniodiol dibenzoate (8) showed the sign of the distinct 1st CE positive around 230 nm in its CD spectrum (Fig. 3) in methanol solution revealing that the two benzoate chromophores of 8 in its more populated

Fig 3 CD Spectrum of (+)-goniodiol dibenzoate (8).

conformer (B) with the two benzoates in the *gauche* conformation must have +ve chirality (+ torsion angle), i.e. must form a right-handed screw pattern. The second weak

CE is observed negative around 215 nm. The *threo* configuration of C-7 and C-8 in 3 has already been ruled out based on the $J_{7,8}$ value (≈ 8 Hz) discussed earlier being supported by the CD study on the molybdenum acetate complex of goniodiol and hence not considered at all.

Thus the following three conformers (A), (B) and (C) of 3 in equilibrium in methanol solution with 7(*R*),8(*R*) *erythro* configuration, viewing from the left side through C₈-C₇ bond, are to be considered (Scheme 4). The groups attached have been designated according to their size, medium (M), large (L) and extra large (L'), the steric bulk order being L' > L > M. The *anti* conformer (A) will not have any intramolecular charge transfer between the benzoate chromophores and hence will exhibit no CE. In the conformer (B), showing the positive CE, Ph(L) becomes more populated than the conformer (C) showing negative CE, wherein the more bulky R' (L) becomes staggered between Ph (L) and OCOPh (M) and Ph staggered between L' and H. Since the major contribution is made by molecules in the conformer (B), the total effect will be the positive Cotton effect, as actually observed.

On the contrary, the mirror image configuration having C-7,C-8 *erythro* and 7(*S*), 8(*S*) configuration will have the conformations (A'), (B') and (C') in equilibrium (Scheme 5). The conformer (A') having the two benzoate chromophores in the *anti* conformation will not exhibit any Cotton effect. The conformer (C') showing positive CE becomes less populated since the most bulky group R' is staggered between OCOPh(M) and Ph(L). The conformer (B') having Ph staggered between L' and M is more populated than conformer (C') and shows negative CE. So, the total effect would be negative CE in contrast to the observed positive CE. So, the possibility of 7(*S*), 8(*S*) *erythro* configuration for (+)-goniodiol (3) or its derivatives is eliminated.

X-Ray crystallographic study of (+)-goniodiol monoacetate (2) : The X-ray crystallographic study of (+)-goniodiol monoacetate (2) unambiguously confirms, as evident from the ORTEP diagram (Fig. 4), the 6,7-*threo* and 7,8-*erythro* relationship with its 6(*R*), 7(*R*), 8(*R*) configuration, and thus supports the biogenetic pathway suggested. The diagram also confirms its *anti* conformation in the crystal lattice corresponding to (a) of Scheme 1 or (A) of Scheme 4.

Scheme 4

Fig 4 ORTEP diagrams of (+)-gonidiol monoacetate (2). (Packing diagrams of SD1 down the A axis)

The structure was solved using the direct methods strategies contained within MULTAN³⁰ and refined by full matrix least-squares refinement with geometrically calculated H-atom positions using SHELXL76³¹.

Experimental

M.ps. measured in open capillary tubes are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were measured on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. ¹H nmr (at 300 MHz) and ¹³C nmr spectra (at 75.5 MHz) were recorded in CDCl₃ on a Bruker-300A

spectrometer; the peak for TMS or solvent (CHCl₃ : δ 7.26) was used as the internal standard and solvent peak (CDCl₃ : δ 77.0) was used as internal standard. Light petrol used had b.p. 60–80°. Silica gel (60–120 mesh, Qualigen) was used for column chromatography, silica gel G for tlc monitoring and silica gel (230–400 mesh, SRL) for flash chromatography in an Eyela EFC-2000 instrument.

Extraction : Isolation of 1, 2 and 3 : A fresh supply of dried and powdered leaves and twigs (1.0 kg) of *G. sesquipedalis* Wall., collected from the hilly areas of

Manipur, were extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with light petrol and chloroform successively for 40 h each. The concentrates of the extracts were separately chromatographed over silica gel columns and the residues of fractions combined by tlc monitoring were subjected to flash chromatography to yield 1 (40 mg), m.p. 150° and 2 (65 mg), 140°, from the petrol extract concentrate, and 3 (21 mg), m.p. 110°, from the chloroform extract concentrate. Compound 4, the presence of which in trace could be detected by tlc in the latter, could not be isolated. Compounds 1, 2 and 3 were characterized by m.ps, m.m.ps. (no depression) and superposable ir spectra with authentic samples¹ available in this laboratory.

Conversion of goniidiol monoacetate (2) to goniidiol (3) : Compound 2 (30 mg) was added to an aqueous solution of NaHCO₃ (10%; 20 ml). The mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 h (monitored by tlc), neutralized with 2N HCl, and extracted with chloroform. The extract after usual washing and drying was concentrated and flash-chromatographed to afford 3 (18 mg), m.p. 110°, characterized by m.p.¹, m.m.p. and superposable ir spectra.

Conversion of 3 to goniidiol dibenzoate (8) : To a solution of 3 (30 mg) in dry pyridine (1 ml), dry benzoyl chloride (2 ml) was added. After the initial reaction had subsided, the reaction mixture was warmed for 10 min and poured with vigorous stirring into ice-cold water (10 ml). The precipitate was allowed to settle, filtered, again stirred thoroughly with saturated sodium carbonate solution (6 ml), filtered, and crystallized from CHCl₃-light petrol to give colourless needles, m.p. 201°; ν_{\max} in cm⁻¹ : 3070w, 2690w, 2560w, 1790m, 1730s (C=O), 1715s (C=O), 1690s, 1600m, 1585m, 1500w, 1450s, 1425m, 1325m, 1290s, 1275s, 1250s, 1240m, 1180, 1110s, 1090m, 1070m, 1030s, 970w, 935m, 900w, 855w, 820m; δ_{H} (300 MHz, CDCl₃; *J* in Hz) 8.04 (2H, dd, *J* 7.8, 1.2, H-2''', H-6'''), 7.80 (2H, dd, *J* 8.1, 1.2, H-2'', H-6'''), 7.14-7.16 (11H, m, all aromatic protons except H-2'', H-6'', H-2''', H-6'''), 6.78 (1H, ddd; *J* 9.3, 5.1, 3.6 Hz, H-4), 6.44 (1H, d, *J* 8.4, H-3), 5.94 (1H, d, *J* 9.9, H-8), 5.72 (1H, dd, *J* 8.4, 2.4, H-7), 4.92 (1H, ddd, *J* 9.6, 6, 2.1) [* assignments are interchangeable]; δ_{C} (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) 121.48 (C-3, 3°), 143.85 (C-4, 3°), 26.31 (C-5, 2°), 73.28^a (C-6, 3°), 74.27^a (C-7, 3°), 74.93^a (C-8, 3°), 164.72^b (-OC OPh at C-7, 4°), 163.12^b (C-2 -OC OPh at C-7, 4°), 136.38 (C-9, 4°), 127.4 (C-10, C-14, 3°), 128.64 (C-11, C-13, 3°), 128.47 (C-12, 3°), 133.38 (C-1'', 4°), 128.34 (C-2'', C-6'', 3°), 133.21 (C-3'', C-5'', 3°), 129.81 (C-4'', 3°) [assignments *ab* are interchangeable].

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grams of goniidiol monoacetate (2) (packing diagrams of SDI down the axis and view of SDI down the least-squares plane) as well as the atomic coordinates for this work. The authors are thankful to Department of Science and Technology, New Delhi, for partly supporting the work by a Research Grant (Project No. SP/SI/G20/93) and to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for the award of a Research Fellowship to one of them (A.P.).

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